

MODEL FOR EVALUATING IOT DEVICES IN SMART LOGISTICS USING THE AHP-TOPSIS APPROACH

ALEKSANDAR LUKOVIĆ¹

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, a.lukovic@sf.bg.ac.rs, 0009-0002-8036-5095

Abstract: *A key element of smart logistics is Internet of Things technology (IoT). To enhance innovation, business efficiency, and the development of new services, it is necessary to develop evaluation models for selecting IoT devices applied in smart logistics. This paper defines a model for evaluating current intelligent IoT devices in the field of smart logistics based on the following criteria: energy consumption, significance of generated data, performance and reliability, scalability, and investment scope, using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Technique of Order Preference Similarity to the Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) methods. The alternatives include IoT devices such as Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, Global Position System (GPS) devices, smart cameras, sensors, and actuators. The AHP method is used to determine the weight coefficients of the criteria and alternatives, while the TOPSIS method ranks IoT devices based on the given criteria, prioritizing their procurement and implementation to improve logistics processes.*

Keywords: *Internet of Things (IoT), smart logistics, Multiple-Criteria Decision Making, AHP-TOPSIS approach*

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern trends in industry and logistics demand increasingly efficient and intelligent systems for managing resources, transport and warehousing. In this context, the concept of smart logistics refers to the integration of information and communication technologies (ICT), the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud infrastructure and big data analytics, with the goal of automating, monitoring, and optimizing processes across the entire logistics chain (Tadejko, 2015; Lu & Teng, 2012; Ivankova et al., 2020).

IoT technologies enable real-time tracking of objects, collection of data from various sensors, and their processing for decision-making in areas such as distribution, route planning, inventory control and cost reduction (Manavalan & Jayakrishna, 2019; Song et al., 2021).

Decision-making in smart logistics often involves multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM), since the evaluation of technologies and devices is based on multiple, often conflicting, criteria such as performance, cost, scalability and reliability. Among the most widely used MCDM methods are the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). The AHP method, initially developed by Saaty (1980) enables hierarchical decomposition of complex problems and the calculation of criteria weights through pairwise comparisons. Similarly, the foundational TOPSIS model was introduced by Hwang and Yoon (1981) to rank alternatives based on their distance from ideal solution. Comprehensive applications and theoretical insights related to AHP are provided by Forman and Gass, and by Ishizaka and Labib (Forman & Gass, 2001; Ishizaka & Labib, 2009).

The aim of this paper is to propose a model for evaluating IoT devices in smart logistics, based on a combined AHP-TOPSIS approach. The model includes relevant decision-making criteria and analyzes concrete IoT technologies with potential application in the logistics sector.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature highlights various models and methods used to support decision-making in logistics, especially those employing multi-criteria approaches. Studies emphasize of AHP for structuring decision hierarchies and of TOPSIS for ranking alternatives close to ideal solution. However, few papers combine these methods for evaluating IoT devices in logistics. This research addresses this gap by proposing a hybrid AHP-TOPSIS model tailored to smart logistics. This section provides an overview of the current research on

the application of multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods, particularly AHP and TOPSIS in the domains of logistics and Internet of Things (IoT). The review in Table 1 aims to contextualize the selected methodology and justify its use in evaluating IoT devices in logistics.

The following selection criteria were applied to the included studies:

Recency (2020 – 2022) – Priority was given to the most recent publications.

Source credibility – Only articles published in reputable peer-reviewed journals or by renowned publishers Elsevier, IEEE, Springer, etc.) were included.

Topical relevance – The study had to address at least one of the following: IoT, logistics, AHP or TOPSIS.

Methodological relevance – The study had to apply AHP and/or TOPSIS methods in the context of decision-making.

Table 1: Comparative Overview of literature on the application of AHP and TOPSIS in logistics and IoT

Ref.	Year	Description	Logistics	IoT	AHP & TOPSIS
Jiménez-Delgado et al. (2020)	2020.	Innovation integration evaluation in logistics	Yes	No	AHP & TOPSIS
Chakraborty & Das (2020)	2020.	Supply chain using RFID, cloud and TOPSIS	Yes	Yes	TOPSIS only
Forcina et al. (2023)	2020.	Safety management in Industry 4.0	Yes	Yes	TOPSIS only
Menon & Ravi (2022)	2022.	Sustainable supplier selection in electronics supply chains	Yes	No	AHP & TOPSIS
Zaher & Eldakhly (2022)	2022.	Evaluation of IoT platforms	No	Yes	TOPSIS only

2.1. Summary and analysis of selected studies

Jiménez-Delgado et al. (2020) – This study evaluates the integration of innovation and management systems in the logistics sector using AHP and TOPSIS to assess the innovation capacity of companies based on criteria such as quality, environmental performance and health and safety.

Chakraborty & Das (2020) – Proposes a new supply chain management model based on RFID, big data and cloud computing. TOPSIS is applied to evaluate supplier preferences based on delivery time, distance, costs and damage risk.

Forcina et al. (2020) – Focuses on identifying the most suitable Industry 4.0 technologies for manufacturing safety management using TOPSIS. Alternatives include IoT, cloud, augmented reality and big data analytics. Cloud ranked highest, followed by IoT.

Menon & Ravi (2022) – Combines AHP and TOPSIS for selecting sustainable suppliers in electronics supply chains. Evaluation is based on four main criteria: economic (price, quality, delivery, flexibility), environmental (pollution management, eco-design), social (human rights, workplace safety), ethical (transparency, conflict of interest). Although IoT is not the focus, the methodology is highly transferable to smart logistics decision-making.

Zaher & Eldakhly (2022) – Proposes a framework for selecting the best IoT platform using eight criteria, including privacy, data transfer and operation management. TOPSIS ranks platforms such as AWS, Microsoft, Google and IBM.

3. METHODOLOGY – AHP-TOPSIS BASED EVALUATION MODEL

This chapter describes the methodological framework applied to evaluate Internet of Things (IoT) devices in the field of smart logistics using a hybrid multi-criteria decision-making approach. The proposed model integrates the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) for determining criteria weights with the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to the Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) to rank alternatives. The model helps decision-makers prioritize IoT devices based on multiple aspects including energy consumption, data significance, performance and reliability, scalability and investment scope.

3.1. Description of the Proposed Model

The general structure of the model is presented in Figure 1, showing a block diagram of the step-by-step evaluation framework.

Figure 1: Model for evaluating IoT devices in smart logistics

The first step in the decision-making process involves establishing an IoT evaluation team, typically composed of engineers and technical experts. The team is responsible for identifying the IoT devices that are relevant to improving business operations and driving innovation. In this study, the following devices are considered as alternatives: RFID tags, GPS devices, smart cameras, sensors and actuators which are described in more details in section 3.3.

The second step is the definition of the goal, criteria and alternatives. The primary goal is to evaluate the selected IoT alternatives based on a predefined set of criteria. The evaluation criteria used in this model are: energy consumption, data significance, performance and reliability, scalability and investment scope.

The fourth step utilized the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to the Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) to rank the IoT alternatives. Using the weighted matrix obtained from AHP, the TOPSIS method identifies the best and worst solutions and calculates the closeness coefficient for each device. The final output is a ranking of devices from the most to the least suitable for deployment in logistics systems, with scores ranging from 1 to 5.

As result of these steps, IoT devices are evaluated and ranked from least to most suitable according to defined criteria. This systematic approach facilitates informed decision-making during the procurement and implementation of IoT technologies in logistics operations.

3.2. Criteria Definition

The selected criteria are: energy consumption, significance of generated data, performance and reliability, scalability and investment scope.

Energy consumption – Efficiency in power usage, especially relevant for low-power devices.

Significance of generated data – Importance and utility of data for further analytics.

Performance and reliability – Operational robustness and service lifetime.

Scalability – Ease of system expansion and integration.

Investment scope – Financial resources required for deployment.

3.3. Alternatives

Five IoT devices are considered: RFID tags, GPS devices, smart cameras, sensors and actuators.

RFID tags – Enable automatic, contactless identification of items using radio signals. Applied in inventory tracking, warehouse automation, quality control and distribution management.

GPS devices – Used for real-time tracking of delivery vehicles, improving safety, responsiveness and transparency to end-users.

Smart cameras – Provide surveillance and anomaly detection in warehouses and vehicles, leveraging video analytics for enhanced security.

Sensors – Monitor environmental conditions (temperature, humidity), detect motion and assist in automating inventory and location tracking.

Actuators – Useful for automation of conveyors and transport equipment, enhance real-time responsiveness and reduce manual labor.

3.4. AHP Weight Calculation

In this study, a reduced AHP scale ranging from 1 to 5 was used instead of the standard Saaty 1-9 scale. This choice simplifies expert judgment and reduces subjectivity, especially in cases where the alternatives do not differ drastically. The use of reduced scales has been supported in literature (Forman & Gass, 2001; Vaidya & Kumar, 2006.; Ishizaka & Labib, 2009). The numerical values of reduced AHP scale are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Reduced AHP Scale with Numerical Values and Descriptive Ratings

Reduced AHP Scale	Definition
1	Equally important
3	More important
5	Significantly more important
1/3	Less important
1/5	Significantly less important

Additional scale values include:

2 – moderate preference relative to the standard value 3

4 – strong preference relative to the standard value 3

½ - moderate preference relative to the standard value 1 and

¼ - strong negative judgment relative to the standard value 1.

The AHP method consists of the following steps:

Step 1: Define criteria and alternatives.

Step 2: Perform pairwise comparisons of the criteria based on the reduced AHP scale from Table 3.

Step 3: Determine the weights coefficients of the criteria and check for consistency using (1) and (2):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (1)$$

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (2)$$

The solution is considered acceptable if the consistency ratio (CR) is less than 0,10.

Step 4: Perform pairwise comparisons of the alternatives for each criterion based on the reduced AHP scale from Table 3.

Step 5: Determine the weights coefficients of the alternatives for each criterion and check for consistency.

Using expert input, a pairwise comparison matrix was constructed. The following weights for criteria and pairwise comparison matrix are shown in Figure 2.

1	0,33	0,25	0,5	0,5	0,08
3	1	0,33	3	2	0,23
4	3	1	3	5	0,45
2	0,33	0,33	1	2	0,14
2	0,5	0,2	0,5	1	0,10
$\lambda_{max} = 5,206$		$CI = 0,05$		$CR = 0,046$	

Figure 2: Pairwise comparison matrix and weights for criteria

Parameters λ_{max} , CI and CR are $\lambda_{max} = 5,206$, $CI = 0,05$ and $CR = 0,046$. Consistency ratio was calculated and found to be less than 0,1 indicating acceptable consistency.

3.5. Global AHP Priorities of Alternatives

Weights were calculated for each alternative per criteria and global priorities were computed as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Global AHP priorities

Alternative	Global AHP Priority
Sensors	0.385
Actuators	0.254
RFID tags	0.181
Smart cameras	0.099
GPS devices	0.081

3.6. TOPSIS Ranking

IoT devices with potential applications in logistics are RFID tags, GPS, smart cameras, sensors and actuators. These devices are alternatives to the AHP and TOPSIS method. The TOPSIS method consist of the following steps:

Step 1: Construct a decision matrix ($n \times m$) based on the given alternatives and criteria.

Step 2: Normalize the decision matrix (3):

$$\bar{X}_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^2}} \quad (3)$$

Step 3: Compute the weighted normalized decision matrix (4)

$$V = [w_{ij}r_{ij}] = [v_{ij}] \quad (4)$$

where the weights w_{ij} are obtained from the AHP method.

Step 4: Determine the positive ideal solution (V_j^+) and the negative ideal solution (V_j^-).

Step 5: Calculate the Euclidean distance from the ideal and negative ideal solutions (5) and (6):

$$S_i^+ = [\sum_{j=1}^m (V_{ij} - V_j^+)^2]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

$$S_i^- = [\sum_{j=1}^m (V_{ij} - V_j^-)^2]^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

Step 6: Compute the relative closeness coefficient P_i , which is used for ranking the IoT devices. Alternatives with a higher value of P_i , will be better ranked (7).

$$P_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-} \quad (7)$$

TOPSIS was applied using the same criteria and alternatives. After normalization and calculation of ideal/negative-ideal distances, the following ranking was obtained in Table 4.

Table 4: TOPSIS ranking

Alternative	Ranking
Sensors	#1
Actuators	#2
RFID tags	#3
Smart cameras	#4
GPS devices	#5

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both AHP and TOPSIS methods ranked sensors as the most suitable device type for implementation in smart logistics. This indicates their high value in performance, scalability and data relevance. Actuators follow due to their integration capabilities, while GPS devices ranked lowest due to lower data significance and limited scalability in smart logistics environments.

The combined model provides a clear, systematic framework for decision makers to select IoT devices according to logistics priorities and strategic objectives. The results obtained in this study are consistent with trends observed in recent literature, where AHP-TOPSIS methodologies have been successfully applied to evaluate decision-making criteria in smart logistics and IoT integration (Menon & Ravi, 2022; Jiménez-Delgado et al., 2020; Forcina et al., 2023).

The use of a simplified AHP scale improved respondent consistency and reduced cognitive load during pairwise comparisons, aligning with recommendations by Forman & Gass (2001) and Ishizaka & Labib (2009). High ranking of scalability and ease of integration suggests that logistics managers prioritize long-term flexibility and compatibility with existing systems.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a hybrid AHP-TOPSIS model for evaluating IoT devices in the context of smart logistics. The model ranks devices based on multiple relevant criteria and supports decision-makers in prioritizing performance and reliability. The proposed methodology can be adapted by logistics companies seeking to implement Industry 4.0 solutions, enabling better alignment between technological capabilities and operational priorities. Moreover, due to its scalability and methodological adaptability, the model can be extended to other domains, such as smart manufacturing, healthcare, smart agriculture, energy and smart grids and smart building infrastructure. Future research may extend this approach by incorporating real-world operational data and considering dynamic logistics conditions.

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